

STUDIES ON SULPHONAMIDES.

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Recently it has been found that 4-aminobenzenesulphonamide possesses a bacteriostatic and bactericidal action against haemolytic streptococci but, in clinical application it is necessary to give large doses of the drug by mouth which is sometimes inconvenient and often may give rise to certain toxic symptoms (*cf.* Colebrook and Kenny, *Lancet*, 1936, *l*, 1273; Discombe, *ibid.*, *l*, 626; Goodman and Levy, *J. Amer. Med. Assoc.*, 1937, *109*, 1005; Bucy, *ibid.*, p. 1007). Another drawback is that for its lower solubility in water (2% at the body temperature) it is difficult to administer it in proper doses by injection. It would now be natural to synthesise other compounds more or less chemically related to it and then to study their chemotherapeutic properties.

As the bactericidal property (*cf.* Buttle and co-workers, *Lancet*, 1936, *l*, 1286; 1937, *l*, 1331) is not exclusively due to the presence of the sulphonamide grouping, $-\text{SO}_2\text{NH}_2$, it was considered to be of interest to replace the amido part by some other group or chain which is known to promote the therapeutic activity in certain other well known drugs. Such groupings were found in 8-aminoquinoline, 6-methoxy-8-aminoquinoline, *p*-anisidine, ethyl *p*-aminobenzoate and δ -diethylaminobutylamine, and accordingly, *p*-acetylaminobenzene-sulphonyl chloride prepared according to the method of Schroeter (*Ber.*, 1906, *39*, 1563), was condensed with the above amino compounds in the way described in the experimental part of the paper. The resulting compounds were hydrolysed by dilute hydrochloric acid to afford the different amides of 4-aminobenzene-sulphonic acid.

The examinations of the bacteriostatic activity of 4-aminobenzenesulphon-8'-quinolyamide and 4-aminobenzenesulphon- δ -diethylaminobutyl amide point to the fact that the replacement of the amido hydrogen of *p*-aminobenzenesulphonamide by other chain or group lowers the activity and increases the toxicity of the compound.

EXPERIMENTAL.

4-Aminobenzenesulphon-8'-quinolyamide.—Freshly distilled 8-aminoquinoline (5 g.) was dissolved in dry benzene (25 c.c.) and was slowly treated with *p*-acetylaminobenzene-sulphonyl chloride (8 g.) without allowing the

temperature to rise. On stirring the colour of the mixture gradually changed from yellow to orange when it was left overnight. Next day the solid was collected; washed first with benzene and next with ether. This was then triturated with ammonia, filtered and crystallised from alcohol in slender needles, m.p. 192°. (Found: N, 12.45. $C_{17}H_{15}O_3N_3S$ requires N, 12.31 per cent). The above acetyl derivative (4 g.) was heated under reflux for about 1½ hours with 20 c.c. of hydrochloric acid (12%). The solution was cooled in ice and slowly treated with ammonia to make it just alkaline; the quinolyl amide, which separated out, was filtered and crystallised from alcohol in clusters of needles, m.p., 193°. (Found: N, 14.51. $C_{15}H_{13}O_3N_3S$ requires N, 14.05 per cent).

The substance is almost insoluble in water, but in presence of 2 mols. of hydrogen chloride it forms almost a colourless solution which can be easily sterilised by heating on the water-bath for 1 hour.

4-Aminobenzenesulphon-6'-methoxy-8'-quinolylamide.—4-Acetylamino-benzene-sulphonyl chloride (4.8 g.) in a suspension of benzene was mixed with a solution of 6-methoxy-8-aminoquinoline (3.5 g.) in benzene and the resulting mixture was warmed to about 40° on a water-bath for about ½ hour and after 12 hours the solid was collected, dissolved in dilute hydrochloric acid and filtered. The filtrate on neutralisation with ammonia afforded the acetyl derivative of the amide. It separated from alcohol as buff-coloured fine crystals, m.p. 222°. (Found: N, 11.50. $C_{18}H_{17}O_4N_3S$ requires N, 11.32 per cent). The acetyl derivative (3.5 g.) was heated with hydrochloric acid (15 c.c., 6%) for 1 hour under reflux, the solution was filtered hot and the filtrate was carefully neutralised with ammonia when the amide separated out. This was crystallised from rectified spirit in microscopic needles, m. p. 189°. (Found: N, 12.90. $C_{16}H_{15}O_3N_3S$ requires N, 12.76 per cent).

4-Aminobenzenesulphon-4'-methoxyphenylamide.—A mixture containing *p*-anisidine (2.6 g.) dissolved in benzene and *p*-acetylamino-sulphonyl chloride (5 g.) was left overnight. Next day the solid separating was collected and crystallised from rectified spirit in small prismatic needles, m.p. 197°. (Found: N, 8.93. $C_{15}H_{16}O_4N_2S$ requires N, 8.75 per cent).

On hydrolysing the product with hydrochloric acid and neutralising the resulting solution with ammonia, aminobenzenesulphonaniside was easily obtained and crystallised from dilute alcohol (4 : 1) in long prismatic needles, m.p. 195°. (Found: N, 10.28. $C_{13}H_{14}O_3N_2S$ requires N, 10.07 per cent).

4-Aminobenzenesulphon-δ-diethylaminobutylamide.—A solution of δ-diethylaminobutylamine (4 g.) in benzene was treated with the acetylsulphonyl

chloride (6.4 g.) as usual. After 24 hours the benzene from the reaction mixture was evaporated off and the residual gummy mass was dissolved in minimum quantity of dilute hydrochloric acid, filtered and the filtrate was kept in *vacuo* over sulphuric acid; crystals gradually separated out and were collected after a fortnight. These were recrystallised from boiling alcohol in clusters of needles, m.p. 172°, and were found to be the hydrochloride of 4-aminobenzenesulphon- δ -diethylaminobutylamide. (Found: N, 12.84; Cl, 10.05. $C_{14}H_{25}O_2N_3S$, HCl requires N, 12.52; Cl, 10.58 per cent).

4-Acetylamino benzenesulphon-4'-carbethoxyphenylamide. — Molecular proportions of 4-acetylamino benzene-sulphonyl chloride and ethyl *p*-aminobenzoate were mixed together in presence of benzene and left overnight. The benzene was evaporated off and the solid was crystallised from alcohol in clusters of microscopic needles, m.p. 220°. (Found: N, 7.72. $C_{17}H_{18}O_5N_2S$ requires N, 7.74 per cent).

In an attempt to condense 2-chloro-5-amino-7-methoxyacridine with 4-acetylamino benzene-sulphonyl chloride in the customary way, the initial condensation product, the acetyl sulphonamide melting at 317°, was isolated, but during its crystallisation from alcohol it decomposed to 2-chloro-7-methoxyacridone. Work is still in progress in this direction.

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Received November 15, 1937.